

MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES OF BRAIN STRUCTURES IN THYROID HORMONE DEFICIENCY

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Annotation. For the clinical part of the study, the results of the examination of 140 women with thyroid gland pathology and 80 healthy pregnant women, and for the experimental part of the study, the results of the morphological and morphometric examination of the brains of 222 rat children were obtained. In different periods of pregnancy, the main anatomical structures of the brain of the fetus, the width of the cavity of the clear membrane, the depth of the sylvian's cleft, the width of the lateral ventricles, the length of the package-like body in the 2nd screening period of pregnancy, and the transverse diameter of the cerebellum in the 3rd screening period were found to grow rapidly; Based on the obtained data, new regional percentiles were developed based on the study of the growth dynamics of anatomical indicators of the fetal brain.

Key words: brain, fetometry, hypothyroidism, screening

МОРФОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ СТРУКТУР МОЗГА ПРИ ДЕФИЦИТЕ ТИРЕОИДНЫХ ГОРМОНОВ

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Аннотация. Для клинической части исследования использованы результаты обследования 140 женщин с патологией щитовидной железы и 80 здоровых беременных, для экспериментальной части исследования - результаты морфологического и морфометрического исследования головного мозга 222 крысиных детей. были получены. В разные сроки беременности основные анатомические структуры головного мозга плода, ширина полости прозрачной оболочки, глубина силвиевых ворот, ширина боковых желудочков, длина паковкообразного тела в на 2-м скрининговом сроке беременности и поперечном диаметре мозжечка на 3-м скрининговом сроке отмечен быстрый рост; На основании полученных данных были разработаны новые региональные процентиля на основе изучения динамики роста анатомических показателей головного мозга плода.

Ключевые слова: головной мозг, фетометрия, гипотиреоз, скрининг.

QALQONSIMON BEZ GORMONI YETISHMASLIGIDA MIYA TUZILISHINING MORFOLOGIK O'ZGARISHI

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Annotatsiya: Tadqiqotning klinik qismi uchun qalqonsimon bez patologiyasi bo'lgan 140 nafar ayol va 80 nafar sog'lom homilador ayollarni tekshirish natijalari, eksperimental qismi uchun esa 222 ta kalamush bolalarning miyasini morfologik va morfometrik tekshirish natijalari qo'lga kiritildi. Homiladorlikning turli davrlarida homila miyasining asosiy anatomik tuzilmalari, shaffof membrana bo'shlig'ining kengligi, sylviev egatining chuqurligi, lateral qorinchalarning kengligi, ichida paketga o'xshash tananing uzunligi. homiladorlikning 2-skrining davri va 3-skrining davrida serebellumning ko'ndalang diametri tez o'sishi aniqlandi; Olingan ma'lumotlarga asoslanib, homila miyasining anatomik ko'rsatkichlarining o'sish dinamikasini o'rganish asosida yangi mintaqaviy foizlar ishlab chiqildi.

Kalit so'zlar: miya, fetometriya, hipotiroidizm, skrining

Relevance of the work: Currently, examination of the fetus by ultrasound is one of the important components of the examination performed during pregnancy. Ultrasound examination of organs and systems of the fetus during these periods allows to identify a large number of congenital malformations. In this case, it is very important to evaluate the structures of the brain of the fetus, because congenital defects of the central nervous system lead to the formation of disabilities in many children [1,2,11], and to death in every third child [4,6,7]. When performing an ultrasound evaluation of the fetal brain, it is of great importance to know the characteristics of its structure depending on the duration of pregnancy, which makes it possible to timely diagnose deviations in the development of brain structures [3,8,10]. During ultrasound examination during the 1st, 2nd and 3rd screening periods of pregnancy, all structures of the brain listed in the protocol must be assessed. In our republic, these structures include evaluation of the lateral ventricles of the brain, the large basin of the brain, the cerebrum, and the clear septal cavity [2,5,9]. In the screening procedure, it is recommended to evaluate these structures visually, without measuring their numerical values.

Materials and methods of research:The research results of 140 patients with thyroid pathology and 80 healthy pregnant women were obtained during 2019-2022. All for research selected pregnant women were strictly monitored. All pregnant women were in the age group of 20 to 35 years, and those with a body weight of 60 kg to 80 kg were selected for the study. Their anamnesis data were collected and singleton women in their first pregnancy without concomitant diseases were selected. Then, pregnant women were divided into 2 groups: the first group was the control group, which consisted of healthy pregnant women; the second group is the observation group, a group of pregnant women who were monitored by an endocrinologist and gynecologist at different periods of pregnancy and diagnosed with hypothyroidism, who started taking levothyroxine at a dose of 50 µg at different periods of pregnancy, since the lack of thyroid hormones was detected [11,12].

Pregnant women at 12-13 and 14-15 weeks (first screening), 20-21 weeks, 22-23 weeks and 24-25 weeks (second screening) , 30-31 weeks, 32-33 weeks and 34-35 weeks (third screening)) the sizes of the anatomical structures of the brain of the fetus were measured using the method of ultrasound diagnostics at the stages of examination. The following anatomical structures of the fetal brain were measured: the width of the cavity of the clear membrane, the biparietal size, the width of the lateral ventricles, the depth of the sylvian ridge, the transverse diameter of the cerebellum, the anterior-posterior size of the cerebellum.

Mathematical statistical analysis was performed using the data of the main fetometric dimensions of the fetus and regional percentiles were developed. Analysis of thyrotropin hormone and free thyrothyronine and thyroxine samples in serum of pregnant women was measured by direct chemiluminescent parametric technology. ECIIA chemiluminescent immunoassay immunochemical analyzers were used. Determination of thyrotropin hormone in the mother's blood is the main indicator in the diagnosis of thyroid gland dysfunction. Small changes in the concentration of free thyroid hormones also lead to opposite changes in the level of thyrotropin. In order to determine the daily rhythm of the thyrotropin hormone in the mother's blood, the maternal serum was taken and examined in the laboratory.

A total of 222 rat pups were used for the experimental part of our research work. 122 rat pups born from experimentally hypothyroid female rats and 100 rat pups from intact female rats were used for the study. The offspring of mother rats in both groups were studied on the 3rd, 7th, 14th, 21st and 28th days of postnatal ontogenesis.

Blood was taken from the tail vein of mother rats, and the amount of thyroid hormones was studied. The observation of various levels of metabolic disturbances in the body due to the lack of thyroid hormones is reported in the literature.

Baby rats were euthanized by decapitation on days 3, 7, 14, 21, and 28 after birth. Tissues were taken from different parts of the brain for histological examination. Brain tissue was fixed in 10% formalin solution, dehydrated in alcohol, and paraffin blocks were prepared. 8-12 μm histological preparations were prepared from the prepared paraffin blocks and stained by the hematoxylin-eosin method. Histological sections prepared on a rotor microtome with a thickness of 5-8 microns were stained with hematoxylin-eosin in a standard way.

The obtained data were determined in the statistical section of Microsoft Excel 2010 as the arithmetic mean M_n , the average error m of the relative sizes, and the accuracy coefficient t . Photomicrographs of histological preparations were captured using a CX40 model OD400 camera microscope.

Results and discussion: The indicators of the anatomical structures of the brain of the fetuses of healthy pregnant women were studied in dynamics during different periods of screening. Evaluation of the gap of the clear membrane in the fetus was determined in all of our observations. The width of the cavity of the fetal clear

membrane increased with the growing period of the fetus . When assessing the width of the diaphragm cavity, the cerebral hemispheres were studied in a symmetrical position at the level of the optic disc. On the basis of the obtained data, regional percentiles about the dimensions of the clear membrane space were created. In the 12-13th week of the 1 screening period, the width of the clear membrane was 1.9 ± 0.03 mm on average, and on average 3.2 ± 1.1 mm in the 14-15 week. In the 22nd - 23rd week of the 2nd screening period, the growth rate reached a high level and it was noted that it increased by 2.2 mm compared to the previous one, i.e. 20-21 weeks. By the 24th - 25th week, the width of the cavity of the clear membrane of the fetus has increased by 1.3 mm compared to the previous period. By screening period 3, it was observed that the width of the clear membrane increased on average by 1.8 mm compared to the indicator of 24-25 weeks of screening period, and at 35-36 weeks it was on average 11.9 ± 1.1 mm (10.8-12.4 mm). According to our plan, the biparietal dimensions of the fetuses of healthy women were measured and it was determined that they were related to the width of the hymen cavity. The biparietal dimension is measured across the two parietal bones of the fetus and is used to estimate fetal weight and gestational age. According to our data, it was found that there is a positive correlation ($r=0.9$) between the width of the fetal diaphragm and biparietal dimensions.

The width of the lateral ventricles was completely visible in all periods of the fetuses of the pregnant women we studied. The dimensions of the lateral ventricles were taken in the axial plane. In the fetuses of women in the control group, the width of the lateral ventricles at 12-13 weeks of screening period 1 was on average 3.9 ± 0.8 mm, and at 14-15 weeks it was from 3.5 mm to 4.9 mm, on average 4.3 ± 0.03 mm. It was found that the width of the lateral ventricles in the period of 20-21 weeks by the 2nd screening period was 4.6 mm to 5.8 mm, on average 5.2 ± 0.7 mm. This indicator showed an increase of 0.9 mm compared to 14-15 weeks of screening period 1. By the 22nd - 23rd week of the 2nd screening period, the width of the lateral ventricles increased by 0.8 mm, and it was noted that the minimum value was 5.4 mm and the maximum value was 6.9 mm. The average was 6.4 ± 0.05 mm. By the 24th - 25th week, the width of the lateral ventricles increased from 6.1 mm to 8.4 mm and was found to be 7.2 ± 0.12 mm on average.

We started measuring the length of the package body from the second screening period, because it was not possible to measure the length of the package body in the first screening periods.

By the second screening period, it was found that the length of the package-like body was equal to 11.6 ± 0.3 mm in the period of 20-21 weeks. By the 22nd - 23rd week of the 2nd screening period, the length of the package body increased reliably ($r<0.05$) by 1.7 mm and was on average 13.3 ± 0.05 mm. By the 24th - 25th week, it was determined that this indicator will be equal to 14.8 mm on average. As the gestation period increased, the length of the package body also increased. By the third screening

period, a 3.4 mm increase in the length of the packing body was observed. And on average 17.6 ± 0.03 at 30-31 weeks was equal to mm. At 32-33 weeks, this indicator is on average 19.8 ± 0.05 was found to be mm. At 35-36 weeks, the length of the package body had the highest growth rate ($r < 0.05$) (+2.6 mm) and the average length was 22.4 ± 1.1 mm.

We also assessed the position of the Sylvie's ethmoid to assess the development of the fetal brain. Sylvie egatin was seen in the fetuses of women in the control group from 16 weeks. Along with the increasing depth of the Sylvie egate, its shape also changed. By the 20th-21st week of the 2nd screening period, the angles of the Sylvie egate are flattened. By 22-23 weeks, Sylvie's edge formed a sharp corner. Later, as the gestation period increased, the angles of Sylvie's angle increased and it was determined that they were equal to 90° at 24-25 weeks. As the gestation period increases, the size of the Sylvie egatine increases, and its angle forms an obtuse angle and forms 135° at 32-33 weeks. Later, from 16 weeks, it was possible to determine in 70% of the studied fetuses. The analysis of the obtained data showed that there is a correlation between Sylvie egati and the duration of pregnancy. With the increase in the gestation period, the index of the depth of the Sylvie egate also increased. The analysis of our data showed that in the 12-13 weeks of the 1 screening period, the size of the Sylvie's egate was on average 7.65 ± 0.005 mm, and by the 14-15 weeks it was equal to 7.9 ± 0.07 mm. 2 during the 22-23 weeks of the screening period, an increase of 3.7 mm was found and averaged 11.5 ± 1.05 mm. By the 22nd - 23rd week of screening 2, the length of the package body increased by 2 mm and averaged 13.5 ± 0.09 mm. By the 24th - 25th week, it was determined that this indicator will be equal to 15 ± 1.3 mm on average. As the period of pregnancy increased, the length of Sylvie's skirt also increased. And at 30-31 weeks, the length of Sylvie egate is 18.3 ± 0.02 on average was equal to mm. At 32-33 weeks, this indicator is on average 19.8 ± 0.01 an increase of mm was noted. At 35-36 weeks, the length of the Sylvie egate had the highest growth rate and the average length was found to be 22.4 ± 1.3 mm.

We determined the measurement of the transverse diameter of the cerebellum from 14-15 weeks of the 1st screening period. During this period, it was determined that the transverse diameter of the cerebrum was from 8 mm to 10.2 mm, and its average value was 9.1 ± 1.2 mm.

10.9 ± 0.6 mm on average at 20-21 weeks of screening period 2. By 22-23 weeks, an increase in the transverse diameter of the cerebellum was observed up to 3.6 mm, and it was noted that it was equal to 14.6 ± 0.8 mm on average during this period. By 24-25 weeks, the diameter of the cerebellum increased by 3 mm and was found to be 17.6 ± 1.2 mm on average.

During the period of 3 screening periods, the growth rate of the diameter of the cerebellum had the highest values. By the 30-31 week period, a reliable ($r < 0.05$) increase in the diameter of the cerebellum by 7 mm compared to the previous period

was observed. By the period of 32-33 weeks, it was determined that the diameter of the brain of the fetus of healthy pregnant women increased reliably ($r < 0.05$) by 5.8 mm and was on average 30.5 ± 1.3 mm. By the end of the 3rd screening period, a decrease in growth rate was observed. Compared to the previous period, there was an increase of 3.1 mm at 35-36 weeks, and this indicator was equal to 33.6 ± 1.1 mm on average.

the diameter of the cerebellum, we developed regional percentiles. These percentiles are the 5th, 50th, and 90th percentiles, covering 90% of the normal population. The analysis of the obtained data showed that the diameter of the cerebellum increased as the gestation period increased. The highest growth rate occurred at screening period 3 (increased from 3.1 mm to 7 mm). The lowest growth rate occurred between the 1st and 2nd screening periods (increased by 1.8 mm).

We evaluated the changes of the clear membrane in the fetuses of women diagnosed with hypothyroidism according to three criteria:

- 1) Absence of the cavity of the clear membrane at all;
- 2) Widening of the hymen cavity compared to the fetus of healthy pregnant women
- 3) Absence of the wall of the hilar cavity.

The width of the cavity of the clear membrane in the fetuses of pregnant women with hypothyroidism was not significantly different from that of the control group during the 1st screening period at 12-13 weeks and was on average 2.0 ± 0.1 mm, and at 14-15 weeks - 3.3 ± 0.03 mm. In the fetuses of pregnant women observed during the 1 screening period, the width of the cavity of the clear membrane was not visualized in 25% of cases, and in 35% of cases the clear membrane was observed.

In the fetuses of pregnant women with hypothyroidism, the width of the lumen of the clear membrane by the 2nd screening period at the period of 20-21 weeks did not differ from that of the control group in 45% of cases and was on average 4.4 ± 0.02 mm. In 55% of cases, it was observed that the cavity of the clear membrane was wider by 0.9 mm compared to that in the fetuses of the control group of the same period, and this indicator was found to be equal to 5.0 ± 0.01 mm on average. By 22-23 weeks, the average of the clear membrane was 6.6 ± 0.06 mm. This indicator was found to be 1.2 mm wider than the control group at 22-23 weeks. By the 24th - 25th week, the width of the clear membrane was found to be 7.4 ± 0.09 mm on average. By this period, the width of the clear membrane was significantly ($r < 0.05$) 1.7 mm wider than that of the control group.

In fetuses of pregnant women with hypothyroidism, the width of the cavity of the clear membrane by the 3rd screening period in the period of 30-31 weeks did not differ from that of the control group in 45% of cases and was equal to 4.4 ± 0.08 mm on average. In 55% of cases, cases of expansion of the clear membrane cavity were observed, and this indicator was found to be equal to 5.0 mm on average. By 22-23 weeks, the width of the clear membrane was 5.9 ± 1.1 mm. This figure was observed

to be 16% wider compared to the control group at 22-23 weeks. By 24-25 weeks, it was found that the width of the clear membrane is from 4.5 to 7.9 mm, the average is 6.7 ± 0.8 mm.

Thus, in the screening period of 1 of the cases we observed, no difference was detected in the clear membrane cavity compared to the fetuses of healthy pregnant women. In the second screening period, in 20-21 weeks, 45% of cases did not differ from the control group, and in 55% of cases, the gap of the clear membrane was observed to be 0.9 mm wider than that of the fetuses of the control group of the same period. By 22-23 weeks, it was observed that the width of the clear membrane was 1.2 mm wider compared to the control group. By 24-25 weeks, the width of the clear membrane was determined to be 1.7 mm compared to the control group.

When the width of the lateral ventricles of the fetuses of women with hypothyroidism was studied, no reliable changes were observed during the 1st screening period compared to the control group. In this period, i.e. 1 screening, at 12-13 weeks, the width of the lateral ventricles was on average 4.1 ± 0.7 mm, and at 14-15 weeks - 4.5 ± 1.2 mm.

By screening period 2, the lateral ventricles of the fetal brain of women with hypothyroidism were found to be larger in 32% of cases at 20-21 weeks than in the control group, and the width ranged from 5.3 mm to 7.3 mm, with an average of 6.9 ± 0.2 mm. was determined. By the 22nd - 23rd week of the 2nd screening period, it was found that the width of the lateral ventricles increased reliably ($r < 0.05$) than in the control group and was on average 8.7 mm (from 6.5 to 9.2 mm). By 24-25 weeks, the width of the lateral ventricles increased by 2.4 mm compared to the control group and averaged 9.6 mm (range 9 to 10.8). A total of 23% of the cases observed by us showed a separate enlargement of the lateral ventricles, and in 77% of the cases, both ventricles were simultaneously enlarged.

By 3 screening periods, the lateral ventricles of the fetuses of women with hypothyroidism were found to be significantly ($r < 0.05$) larger at 20-21 weeks than those of the control group, and the width ranged from 5.3 mm to 7.3 mm, with an average of 6.9 ± 0.02 mm was found to be equal. By the 22nd - 23rd week of screening, it was found that the width of the lateral ventricles increased reliably ($r < 0.05$) than in the control group and was on average 8.7 mm (from 6.5 to 9.2 mm). By the 24th - 25th week, the width of the lateral ventricles was observed to increase by 2.4 mm compared to the control group and was equal to 9.6 ± 0.2 mm on average (min 9 to 10.8). A total of 15% of the cases observed by us showed a separate expansion of the lateral ventricles, and in 75% of the cases both ventricles were simultaneously expanded. In 30% of cases monitored in dynamics, both ventricles were dilated.

With the increase in the gestation period, the index of the depth of the Sylvian fissure also increased. It was found that the depth of the Sylvian fissure did not exceed 4-5 mm compared to the control group. During the 2nd screening period, in 25% of cases,

the shape of the sylviev's uterus did not correspond to the gestation period of the fetus. In the period of 30-31 weeks of the 3 screening period, it was found that in 3 fetuses, expansion of the lateral ventricles and the incompatibility of the shape of the sylviev's egate were found together.

During the macroscopic study of the brain, the smoothness of the egates and pus of the brain indicated an increase in fluid in the brain tissue. In different periods of the experiment, different microscopic changes were observed in the brain tissue. Changes in the blood vessels of the brain were observed from the 7th day of postnatal ontogeny.

By the 14th day of the experiment, swelling in the perivascular area of the hemispheres of the brain, accumulation of fluid around the capillaries was detected. Dystrophic changes were observed in blood vessels, blood coagulation and endotheliocytes. The appearance of small vacuoles was observed in astrocytes and oligodendrogliaocytes (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. In the white matter of the brain, cell reduction and vacuolization are seen. Staining: hematoxylin-eosin. X: ok.10, ob 20

By the 21st day of the experiment, an increase in pervascular and pericellular swelling in the brain was observed. It was found that a cavity filled with a small volume of liquid appeared in the white matter of the brain. Lysis of nerve cells and fibers is observed in this branch of the brain. Vacuoles appear in the cytoplasm of nerve cells, the borders of the cells are not clear. Lightening of the cytoplasm of cells was observed due to tigrolysis. It can be seen that the nuclei of the cells are hyperchromic, basophilic, and have an angular shape. A tumor of glial cells was detected. Astrocytes and oligodendrogliaocytes are vacuolated. The nucleus is pyknotic. Tumors of glial cells were detected. Fibrillation of nerve fibers was observed, accumulation of edema fluid between fibrils was observed. changes were more pronounced in the white brain compared to the cerebral cortex.

By the 28th day of the experiment, an increase in pervascular and pericellular swelling in the brain was observed. It was found that a cavity filled with a small volume

of liquid appeared in the white matter of the brain. Lysis of nerve cells and fibers is observed in this branch of the brain. Vacuoles appear in the cytoplasm of nerve cells, and the boundaries of the cells are not clear. Lightening of the cytoplasm of cells was observed due to tigrolysis. It can be seen that the nuclei of the cells are hyperchromic, basophilic, and have an angular shape. Tumor of glial cells was detected. Astrocytes and oligodendrogliaocytes are vacuolated. The nucleus is pyknotic. Tumors of glial cells were detected. Fibrillation of nerve fibers was observed, and accumulation of edema fluid between the fibrils was observed (Fig. 2). The observed changes were more pronounced in the white brain compared to the cerebral cortex.

**Figure 2. Dampness in blood vessels, edema in the perivascular area.
Staining: hematoxylin-eosin. X: ok.10, ob 20**

Morphometric examinations showed a decrease in the area of nerve cells and nerve cells per 1 mm^2 with deepening of the process in the case of experimental hypothyroidism. It was found that the number of nerve cells in the brain of the control group was 214.3 ± 10.2 , and the area of the nucleus of nerve cells was $192.3 \pm 5.1 \mu\text{m}^2$. In the experimental group, these indicators were not significantly different. It was noted that the number of nerve cells in the brain of rat children in the experimental group was 212.3 ± 9.6 per 1 mm^2 and the area of the nucleus of nerve cells was $191.9 \pm 6.3 \mu\text{m}^2$.

By the 14-day period, it was observed that the number of nerve cells in the brain of the experimental group was 209.6 ± 7.5 per 1 mm^2 , and the area of the nucleus of nerve cells was equal to $180.1 \pm 5.6 \mu\text{m}^2$. During this period, compared to the control group, the number of nerve cells decreased by 2%, and the area of the nucleus of nerve cells decreased by 6%.

By the 21st day of the experiment, it was observed that the number of nerve cells in the brain of rat children was 186.9 ± 11.6 per 1 mm^2 , and the area of the nucleus of nerve cells was equal to $170.3 \pm 7.2 \mu\text{m}^2$. During this period, compared to the control

group, the number of nerve cells decreased by 14%, and the area of the nucleus of nerve cells decreased by 12%.

By the 28th day of the experiment, the number of nerve cells decreased by 31%, and the area of the nucleus of nerve cells decreased by 20%.

CONCLUSIONS

A complete assessment of the fetal brain occurs at 15-16 weeks of pregnancy. The most intensive period of measurements of anatomical structures of the brain of healthy female fetuses (20-21, 22-23, 24-25 weeks) corresponded to the 2nd screening period. Data on the size of the brain of the fetus of healthy pregnant women and the developed percentiles will be a guide in the assessment of the size of the anatomical structures of the brain of the fetus. Fetometric indicators of fetuses of hypothyroid women are statistically ($R < 0.05$) greater than those of healthy pregnant women. The expansion of the cavity of the clear membrane of the fetus was observed in 80% of the cases, and the expansion of the lateral ventricles was observed in 40% of the cases. These changes were especially evident during the 2nd screening period. During the 2nd screening period, in 25% of cases, the shape of the Sylvius's ventricle did not correspond to the gestation period of the fetus. It was found that the depth of the Sylvius's ventricle did not exceed 4-5 mm compared to the control group. During the 2nd screening period, in 25% of cases, the shape of the Sylvius's ventricle did not correspond to the gestation period of the fetus. In the period of 30-31 weeks of the 3rd screening period, it was found that in 3 fetuses, expansion of the lateral ventricles and the incompatibility of the shape of the Sylvius's ventricle were found together. In the case of experimental hypothyroidism, swelling of connective tissue fibers, tearing of collagen fibers, compression of cells with swelling material, deformation and atrophy develop.

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